

CAUSES AND FACTORS OF STRESS IN PERSONAL PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY

Jumanova U.S.

GulDU, Trainee researcher of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11176114>

Abstract. *This article is aimed at studying the causes and factors of stress in personal professional activity, which is one of the urgent problems of today, as well as preventing stress in personal professional activity and increasing resistance to stressful situations. About biological and psychological stress that causes specific and non-specific physiological, psychological and behavioral reactions in the human body in modern conditions.*

Keywords: *emotion, psychosomatic, stereotypes, exhaustion, resistance, burnout, Anxiety stage, pressure, eustress, distress.*

Introduction. Today, stress in a person's professional activity is a theoretical and practical psychological problem all over the world. According to statistics, workplace stress causes 30% of employees to leave their jobs. Along with development and growth in political, economic, technical and other fields, there are crisis situations on the world scale. Due to these crises, it is often observed that people fall into stressful situations. This is certainly caused by environmental degradation, harsh rhythm of urban life, aggressive social environment, political instability, financial crises and many other similar factors. As a result, stress managed to become a constant companion of human life.

In modern conditions, the human body is under the influence of biological and psychological stress factors that cause specific and non-specific physiological, psychological and behavioral reactions. These reactions, which have a double role, on the one hand, help to adapt to changing conditions, on the other hand, lead to the emergence of pathological and psychosomatic diseases. The change of the mental paradigm observed in recent years - from nosocentric to adaptation - has drawn the attention of researchers to the study of psychogenic adaptation processes, in particular, the problems of coping with stress as one of the determinants of health and disease.

Scientists believe that minor stresses are inevitable and harmless, but too much stress can cause major, immediate problems for individuals and groups. Stress is such a condition that it causes disorder in the human psyche and body. In unfavorable situations, situations, as a result of increased threats and pressure, a person cannot do anything, cannot run away, cannot say anything, resulting in a stressful situation in people. Initial work on stress was carried out by G. Selye. Stress theory was proposed by G. Selye in 1936, published in 1950, and its most complete presentation and development is reflected in the author's later works [393-397, etc.]. Stress Since the concept was first named and described by G. Selye (1960), various definitions of stress have been developed.

In the theory of G. Selye, stress is considered in terms of physiological reaction to physical, chemical and organic factors. The main content of the theory can be summarized in four positions.

1. All biological organisms have innate mechanisms for maintaining the internal or equilibrium state of their systems. Maintenance of internal balance is provided by homeostasis processes. Maintaining homeostasis is a vital function of the body.

2. Stress factors, i.e. strong external stimuli disturb the internal balance. The body responds to any stress factor, pleasant or unpleasant, with a non-specific physiological arousal. This reaction is protective-adaptive.

goes through several stages. The flow and the time of transition to each stage depends on the level of resistance of the body, the intensity and duration of the stress factor.

4. The body has limited reserves of adaptive capacity to prevent and stop stress - their reduction can lead to illness and death.

Summarizing the results of the research allowed G. Selye to justify the existence of three stages of the process called general adaptation syndrome.

The anxiety stage occurs when a stressor is first observed. In a short time, the resistance level of the body decreases, some somatic and vegetative functions are disturbed. The body then mobilizes reserves and includes mechanisms for self-regulation of defense processes. If the defense reactions are effective, the anxiety subsides and the body returns to normal functioning. Many stresses are resolved at this stage. Such short-term stresses can be called acute stress reactions.

occurs when it is necessary to maintain the body's protective reactions and long-term exposure to the stressor. There is a balanced consumption of adaptive reserves against the background of tension corresponding to the external conditions of functional systems.

Fatigue stage - reflects the violation of the body's protective-adaptive fighting mechanisms due to excessively intensive and long-term effects of stress factors. Adaptation reserves are significantly reduced. The resistance of the body decreases, as a result of which there may be not only functional disorders, but also morphological changes in the body.

G. Selye [164] suggested a distinction between "surface" and "deep" adaptation energy. The first is available "on demand" and the other can be filled due to "deep". The latter is mobilized by adaptive restructuring of the body's homeostatic mechanisms. According to G. Selye, his exhaustion is irreversible and leads to death or aging. As L. L. Kitaev -Smyk [91] noted, many researchers [127, 187] support the assumption that there are two mobilization levels of adaptation. At present, the first stage of stress development - the stage of mobilization of adaptive reserves "anxiety" is relatively well studied, during which the formation of a new "functional system" of the body, which mainly meets the new extreme requirements of the environment, ends. The second and third stages of the development of stress, that is, the stage of sustainable consumption of adaptive reserves and the stage of their destruction, are devoted to several studies. In stress - this is a concept that is lost with an excessively large or excessively small range of observed symptoms. The theoretical constructions of G. Selye include the relativity of causes and the appropriateness of stress. About the concept of stress carrier integrity; states that "these are local structures in the body with local adaptation syndrome, the whole organism responding to the general adaptation syndrome, this or that group of people with socio-psychological manifestations of emotional stress." Under the influence of G. Selye's views, the attention of many researchers was focused on physiological, biological or morphological changes caused by stress factors. At the same time, the dynamics of the relationship of the body's reactions to the provoking cause (stress effect) and the internal, psychological factors of this person disappear into the background. Hormonal, metabolic, neurochemical shifts in the development of emotional stress are being studied in detail, but there are not enough systematic studies to evaluate the dynamics of the body's physiological reactions

and the characteristics of adaptive behavior and the relationship with the emotional state in different periods of exposure to stress stimuli.

The results obtained and their analysis: Research and collection of empirical data was carried out for three months. The main difficulties of the topics were related to the volume of the proposed techniques. The motivation for completing the tasks for each participant of the study was a psychological conclusion according to the methodology, and it was the main one for the subjects during the study, which in turn was a guarantee of interest and qualitative and correct answers.

Table 1 shows the results of the assessment of occupational stress in the questionnaire of K. Weissman.

Occupational stress	High	55%
	Medium	27.5%
	Low	17.5%

Based on the results presented in Table 1, it can be noted that the majority of food service professionals experience high levels of occupational stress (55% of the sample). They cause this emotional state, firstly, to a high degree of overloading of work and obligations during the working day, and secondly, to the inability to influence the decisions and actions of the direct supervisor. The large amount of work that waiters, chefs, and restaurant managers have to do directly affects the quality of its performance, and the anxiety associated with this situation also contributes to increasing the level of occupational stress. Employees of catering organizations with a high level of occupational stress say that they often have to do things that contradict their judgment at work, and that the specifics and schedule of work have a negative impact on personal and family life does.

The average level of occupational stress was found in 27.5% of employees working in the field of catering. The respondents of this sample group note the following factors that lead to the development of professional stress, because the inability to meet the conflicting demands of different people in the professional environment, from time to time they have unpleasant feelings about their official duties and relationships with colleagues often become tense, experts work mainly in conflict and pre-conflict situations. For 17.5 percent of the research participants, professional activity in the field of catering does not develop occupational stress. They are sufficiently aware of the opportunities for professional, career and financial growth in this field of activity, successfully and effectively cope with their work obligations during the working day, establish harmonious relations with colleagues, managers, as well as customers. In general, to emphasize that professionals of this category successfully cope with difficult and stressful situations of various origins in the performance of their professional duties.

Conclusion. The work of representatives of many professions is often associated with high social activity of the subject, many contacts and relationships. Representatives of the catering industry - waiters, cooks, administrators are not excluded. The work of this group of people is directly related to the performance of specific functions of institutions and includes harmful factors of production that professionals encounter at work. Analyzing and summarizing the ideas developed within the framework of the considered approaches, we note that the problem of psychological health of representatives of various specialties in the psychological literature is being actively developed, and the specific characteristics of specialists in the field of nutrition have recently come to the attention of researchers.

As a result of the study of the specific characteristics of the relationship between professional stress and psychological health of catering professionals, the following was determined:

1. The majority of food service professionals have a high level of occupational stress (55% of the sample). They cause this emotional state, firstly, to a high degree of overloading of work and obligations during the working day, and secondly, to the inability to influence the decisions and actions of the direct supervisor. Waiters experience more professional stress than administrators.

2. According to the number methodology, the most acceptable indicator among the representatives of professions in the field of catering is "activity". Mood dominates changeable, they have difficulties in identifying and evaluating it. What is least convenient for nutritionists is well-being manifested in physiological and psychological discomfort.

3. In the study of self-relation, high values have dimensions of "isolation" and "self-confidence". The "self-acceptance" scale has low values, which indicates a general negative background of self-perception, a tendency to be overly critical of oneself. Self-compassion is insufficiently expressed, usually appears episodically.

4. Correlational analysis shows that there is a reliable direct and inverse relationship between occupational stress and aspects of psychological health, such as psycho-emotional state and dignity of employees in the catering industry. Well-being and mood as a component of a person's psycho-emotional state are inversely proportional to the severity of occupational stress. Directly related to occupational stress is an indicator of psycho-emotional state such as "activity".

The problem of occupational stress of many professions is being actively developed in the psychological literature, but the characteristics of its employees in the field of nutrition have only recently come to the attention of researchers.

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